

FACTORISATION OF $X^n - \alpha$ OVER FINITE FIELDS

ABSTRACT. In this note we are studying with basic tools the order of the irreducible factors of polynomials $X^n - \alpha$ over finite fields \mathbb{F}_p . The paper only use basic concepts of finite fields theory. All follows from the fact that $X^n - \alpha$ divides $X^{n^l} - 1$ if α is a l -root of unity and from the other fact, proved below (and consequence of the cyclicity of the subset of invertible elements in finite field), that all the polynomials $X^n - \alpha$ with α a primitive l -root have irreducible factors with the same distribution of orders.

1. INTRODUCTION

The irreducible factorization of polynomials $X^n - 1$ is well known since a long time, which can be sum up with $X^n - 1 = \prod_{d|n} \phi_d$. The factors ϕ_d are called the cyclotomic polynomials. They can be easily calculated by induction and have degree $\varphi(n)$ where φ is called the Euler totient function, $\varphi(n)$ being equal to the cardinal of \mathbb{Z}_n^* (for more brevity the quotient rings $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$ are noted \mathbb{Z}_n). In \mathbb{Z} it can be proved that these polynomials are irreducible. In finite fields it's not the case, but we know that their irreducible factors all have degree the order of p in \mathbb{Z}_n^* (noted $\text{ord}_{\mathbb{Z}_n^*}(p)$). We will note these polynomials $\phi_{d,i}$. As all invertible elements of finite fields are roots of unity, all irreducible polynomials P are of the form $\phi_{d,i}$ for given d and i . We will call d the **order** of P . In this paper we are interested in finding the orders of the irreducible factors of the polynomials $X^n - \alpha$ where $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}_p^*$.

All results here are basics and could surely be established by more advanced mathematical tools.

2. A FIRST EXAMPLE

Let us factoring the polynomial $X^6 + 1$ over \mathbb{F}_5 . We can reasoning with roots: if $\zeta \in \overline{\mathbb{F}_5}$ is a root of $X^6 + 1$ then $\zeta^6 = -1$ so $\zeta^{12} = 1$ and $\zeta^6 \neq 1$. As a result the factors of $X^6 + 1$ are the factors of order $o \mid 12$ with $o \nmid 6$. The only possibilities are $o = 4$ or $o = 12$. Otherwise we can reasoning with factorization directly: we have $(X^6 - 1)(X^6 + 1) = X^{12} - 1$, hence

$$X^6 + 1 = \frac{X^{12} - 1}{X^6 - 1} = \prod_{\substack{k \mid 12 \\ k \nmid 6}} \phi_k = \phi_4 \phi_{12}$$

To get the irreducible factorization recall that polynomial of order 4 have degree $\text{ord}_{\mathbb{Z}_4^*}(5) = 1$, as we can see with $\phi_4 = X^2 + 1 = (X - 2)(X + 2)$. The polynomials of order 12 have degree $\text{ord}_{\mathbb{Z}_{12}^*}(5) = 2$ and $\deg(\phi_{12}) = \varphi(12) = 4$ so $\phi_{12} = \phi_{12,1} \phi_{12,2}$. As a result

$$X^6 + 1 = (X - 2)(X + 2)\phi_{12,1}\phi_{12,2}$$

So $X^6 + 1$ has two degree 1 factors of order 4 and two degree 2 factors of order 12.

3. SECOND EXAMPLE MODULO 5

3.1. First factorization. Let us now factoring $X^6 - 2$ and $X^6 - 3$ over \mathbb{F}_5 . As 2 and 3 are fourth primitive roots we get without difficulty that

$$X^{24} - 1 = (X^6 - 1)(X^6 - 2)(X^6 - 3)(X^6 + 1)$$

so that

$$(X^6 - 2)(X^6 - 3) = \frac{X^{24} - 1}{X^{12} - 1} = \prod_{\substack{k|24 \\ k \nmid 12}} \phi_k = \phi_{24}\phi_8$$

As $\varphi(24) = 8$, $\varphi(8) = 4$, $\text{ord}_{\mathbb{Z}_{24}^*}(5) = 2$ and $\text{ord}_{\mathbb{Z}_8^*}(5) = 2$ then

$$(X^6 - 2)(X^6 - 3) = \phi_{24,1}\phi_{24,2}\phi_{24,3}\phi_{24,4}\phi_{8,1}\phi_{8,2}$$

The question is now: how the factors $\phi_{24,i}$ and $\phi_{8,j}$ are distributed in $X^6 - 2$ and $X^6 - 3$?

3.2. Equidistribution. As \mathbb{F}_{25}^* is cyclic, let β be a generator of \mathbb{F}_{25}^* . The multiplicative order of β is 24 so β^6 has order 4 so $\beta^6 \in \{2, 3\}$. Let us remark that $2^3 = 3$ so $2^7 = 3$ hence if $\beta^6 = 2$ then $(\beta^7)^6 = 3$ and β^7 has multiplicative order 24 to. If $\beta^6 = 3$ the same is true: $(\beta^7)^6 = 2$ and β^7 has multiplicative order 24. As a result there are effectively β of order 24 with $\beta^6 = 2$ or $\beta^6 = 3$.

Let us now take the notation $R_\alpha^6 = \{\zeta \mid \zeta^6 = \alpha\}$. Answer the question above comes down to find the order of the elements of R_α^6 . For that, consider the following commutative diagram:

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} & & x & \longrightarrow & x^6 & & \\ & & \uparrow & & \uparrow & & \\ & \beta^k & \mathbb{F}_{25}^* & \longrightarrow & \mathbb{F}_5^* & \alpha^q & \\ & \uparrow & \uparrow \psi & & \uparrow \wr & \uparrow & \\ & k & \mathbb{Z}_{24} & \xrightarrow{\text{mod } 4} & \mathbb{Z}_4 & q & \end{array}$$

We want to translate the subset R_α^6 into \mathbb{Z}_{24} with ψ :

$$(\beta^k)^6 = \alpha \iff (\beta^6)^k = \alpha \iff \alpha^k = \alpha \iff k \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$$

so $\psi^{-1}(R_\alpha^6) = \{k \in \mathbb{Z}_{24} \mid k \equiv 1 \pmod{4}\}$. As ψ is an isomorphism then it preserve the order and we can inspect the (multiplicative) order of the roots of $X^6 - \alpha$ by inspecting the order in \mathbb{Z}_{24} of the elements of $\{k \mid k \equiv 1 \pmod{4}\}$:

\mathbb{Z}_{24}	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23
order		24			24				8				24				24					8		

So $X^6 - \alpha$ has 4 roots of order 24 and 2 roots of order 8. As a result

$$X^6 - \alpha = \phi_{24,1}\phi_{24,2}\phi_{8,1}$$

This reasoning doesn't depend if α is 2 or 3, which proves that the orders of the irreducible factors of $X^6 - 2$ and $X^6 - 3$ are the same. Note that we have not actually factor these polynomials, but only find the orders of the irreducible factors.

4. GENERAL CASE

Let p a prime integer, n an integer coprime with p and α in \mathbb{F}_p^* .

4.1. First factorization. As $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}_p^*$, then α is of multiplicative order l a divisor of $p - 1$. Let us note R_1^l the l -th roots of unity and P_1^l the l -th primitive roots of unity. These sets are subsets of \mathbb{F}_p^* . We have $\prod_{\alpha \in R_1^l} X - \alpha = X^l - \alpha$ so that $\prod_{\alpha \in R_1^l} X^n - \alpha = X^{nl} - \alpha$. Let us note for all $k \neq 0$, F^k the set of all irreducible factors of $X^k - 1$. With the above formula we get by induction that the irreducible factors of $\prod_{\gamma \in P_1^l} X^n - \gamma$ are the polynomials of

$$F^{nl} \setminus \bigcup_{d \mid l, d \neq l} F^{nd}$$

For example in \mathbb{F}_{11} there are $\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_4$ of order $l = 10$ and with $n = 6$ this gives that the irreducible factors of $(X^6 - \gamma_1) \dots (X^6 - \gamma_4)$ are the elements of $F^{10 \times 6} \setminus (F^{1 \times 6} \cup F^{2 \times 6} \cup F^{5 \times 6}) = F^{10 \times 6} \setminus (F^{2 \times 6} \cup F^{5 \times 6})$ which are the irreducible factors of the ϕ_d with $d \mid 2^2 \times 3 \times 5$, $d \nmid 2 \times 3 \times 5$ and $d \nmid 2^2 \times 3$ i.e. the irreducible factors of ϕ_{20} and ϕ_{60} .

4.2. Equidistribution. We prove now that all the different polynomials $X^n - \alpha$ with α primitive l -root have irreducible factors with the same distribution of orders. Let us note $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_l$ the primitive l -roots of \mathbb{F}_p i.e. as we note above, the members of $P_1^l \subseteq \mathbb{F}_p^*$. Let us note $R_\alpha^n = \{\zeta \in \overline{\mathbb{F}_p} \mid \zeta^n = \alpha\}$. As $\alpha^l = 1$ then $R_\alpha^n \subseteq R_1^{nl}$. As there exists d such that $R_1^{nl} \subseteq \mathbb{F}_{p^d}^*$, and the later being cyclic, the set R_1^{nl} is generated by β primitive nl -root and β^n is of order l so $\beta^n = \alpha \in P_1^l$. We have then the following commutative diagram:

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc}
 & & \zeta & \xrightarrow{\quad} & \zeta^n & & \\
 & & & & & & \\
 \beta^k & & R_1^{nl} & \xrightarrow{\quad} & R_1^l & & \alpha^q \\
 \uparrow & & \uparrow \psi & & \uparrow \wr & & \uparrow \\
 k & & \mathbb{Z}_{nl} & \xrightarrow{\text{mod } l} & \mathbb{Z}_l & & q
 \end{array}$$

Moreover

$$(\beta^k)^n = \alpha \iff (\beta^n)^k = \alpha \iff \alpha^k = \alpha \iff k \equiv 1 \pmod{l}$$

and hence $\psi^{-1}(R_\alpha^n) = \{k \in \mathbb{Z}_{nl} \mid k \equiv 1 \pmod{l}\}$. The morphism ψ being an isomorphism, it preserve the order, and so the multiplicative order of the roots of $X^n - \alpha$ are given by the orders of the elements of $\{k \in \mathbb{Z}_{nl} \mid k \equiv 1 \pmod{l}\}$.

This reasoning fits for all $\alpha \in P_1^l$ with $\beta \in R_1^{nl}$ such that $\beta^n = \alpha$. Let us show that for all $\alpha \in P_1^l$ there exists such a β : we already know that there is at least one $\alpha \in P_1^l$ for which there exists $\beta \in R_1^{nl}$ such that $\beta^n = \alpha$. Let α' be an other element of P_1^l . As α is a generator of R_1^l then there is q such that $\alpha^q = \alpha'$ with q coprime with l , α' being also of order l . We will also have that for all r , $\alpha^{q+rl} = \alpha'$. As a result $(\beta^{q+rl})^n = \alpha'$. It remains to show that there exists r such that β^{q+rl} is also of order nl . It will be so if $q + rl$ is coprime with nl . So we look for $q' \equiv q \pmod{l}$ and q' coprime with nl , which will be easily find using chinese remainder theorem.

4.3. Illustration of the results. Let us find the repartition of orders in the irreducible factorization of $X^6 - 2$ in \mathbb{F}_{11} . The element 2 has order 10 in \mathbb{F}_{11}^* and there are four such elements $\gamma_1 = 2, \dots, \gamma_4$ in \mathbb{F}_{11}^* . We have seen above that the irreducible factors of $(X^6 - \gamma_1) \dots (X^6 - \gamma_4)$ are $F^{10 \times 6} \setminus (F^{1 \times 10} \cup F^{2 \times 10} \cup F^{5 \times 10})$ i.e. the irreducible factors of ϕ_{60} and ϕ_{20} . We have also seen that each polynomial $X^6 - \gamma_i$ has the same number of factors of each order and we show easily that $\phi_{60} = \phi_{60,1} \dots, \phi_{60,8}$ and $\phi_{20} = \phi_{20,1} \dots \phi_{20,4}$, all factors here being of degree 2. As a result $X^6 - 2 = \phi_{60,1} \phi_{60,2} \phi_{20,1}$. In conclusion $X^6 - 2$ has two degree 2 factors of order 60 and one degree 2 factor of order 20.

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